

Project information

Project full title	LEAPS pilot to foster open innovation for accelerator-based light sources in Europe
Project acronym	LEAPS-INNOV
Grant agreement no.	101004728
Instrument	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Duration	01/04/2021 – 31/03/2025
Website	https://www.leaps-innov.eu/

Deliverable information

Deliverable no.	D1.2
Deliverable title	Innovation Advisory Board ToR
Deliverable responsible	DESY
Related Work-Package/Task	WP1
Type (e.g. Report; other)	Other
Author(s)	Julia Hauk
Dissemination level	Public
Document Version	V0.2
Date	12 July 2021
Download page	https://www.leaps-innov.eu/

Document information

Version no.	Date	Author(s)	Comment
V0.1	17 June 2021	Julia Hauk	Ute Krell, Elke Plönjes
V0.2	12 July 2021	Julia Hauk	Alejandro Sanchez, Elizabeth Shotton, Elke Plönjes
Vo.3	23 Sep 2021	Julia Hauk	

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LEAPS-INNOV Innovation Advisory Board

Terms of Reference (ToR)

Introduction/Purpose

LEAPS-INNOV (www.leaps-innov.eu) is a four-year Horizon 2020 EU project aiming at implementing new strategies and activities for long-term partnerships between industry and European light sources, specifically synchrotrons and free electron lasers, with their thousands of users from academia, research institutions and industry.

A significant piece of the governance structure of LEAPS-INNOV (see figure 1 below) is an Innovation Advisory Board (IAB), which will consult with the LEAPS-INNOV governing and executive boards on technological and innovation matters of this pilot project with special focus on establishing sustainable long-term innovation in the European photon science community. The IAB shall be composed of independent, high-level, international experts from industry and academia.

Fig. 1 LEAPS-INNOV Governance structure

Charge to the Board

The IAB will give advice to the LEAPS-INNOV governing and executive boards on various matters related to the innovation strategy of LEAPS-INNOV where appropriate. This is expected to be an ongoing process to ensure constant evaluation of the LEAPS-INNOV measures and progress. In particular, the following tasks are foreseen:

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101004728

- Advise on the LEAPS-INNOV innovation strategy and on how innovation needs are addressed in the WPs
- Advise on measures enhancing the innovation approach (progressive activities)
- Advise on how to jointly drive new technologies forward and ensure technological developments
- Exchange of experience and best practise
- Advise on suitable success measures for the LEAPS-INNOV project where applicable
- Advise on how to effectively integrate industry into LEAPS-INNOV events, such as annual meetings, WP workshops and co-creation roundtables (WP9)
- Advise on which additional stakeholders and initiatives could be addressed
- Advise on LEAPS innovation strategy to be drafted in WP8

IAB Members

The IAB is composed of independent, high-level, international experts from industry and academia, with approximately 7 to 15 experts in total. Experts from outside Europe may also be considered as IAB members.

1-2 independent experts per work package (except WP1) are nominated and approved (with a two-thirds majority) by the LEAPS-INNOV governing board for a two-year term that is renewable. If deemed necessary, the LEAPS-INNOV governing board and/or executive board may suggest additional experts.

The IAB elects a chair and two deputies among its members by a single majority of the votes cast. The chair of the IAB and the deputies of the chair shall be allowed to attend the meetings of the governing board as observers without voting rights.

Each Innovation Advisory Board member will sign a confidentiality declaration. Due to its character as an external and independent committee, proposed IAB members cannot be employed with one of the 22 consortium partners of LEAPS-INNOV, at the time of their approval.

Mode of Operation and Meetings

The IAB will meet regularly once a year, face-to-face (if possible) during a LEAPS-INNOV annual meeting. Additional digital meeting(s) can be scheduled if required. The IAB chair is invited as a guest to the governing board meetings (once a year during the annual meeting). The IAB will compile recommendations to the consortium after each meeting based on the tasks above. A two-third participation of members is required to constitute a regular IAB meeting. Extraordinary IAB meetings may be requested by the governing board or executive board, if issues of significant importance have to be considered.

The IAB elects a chair and deputies for a two-year term, renewable, during the first IAB meeting.

The IAB is supported by members of the project management team at DESY. The coordinator, DESY, invites members to the IAB meetings and writes the minutes of the meetings. The coordinator

communicates the findings and recommendations to the governing board and executive board and, where appropriate, prepares the implementation/ follows up on of the suggestions made by the IAB. The Coordinator provides sufficient information on the LEAPS-INNOV project and its progress to the IAB members.

Annex: LEAPS-INNOV confidentiality declaration V0.3 final, as agreed by LEAPS-INNOV beneficiaries.

CONFIDENTIALITY DECLARATION

Confidential Information: All information in whatever form or mode of communication, which is not yet in the public domain and is disclosed in connection with the LEAPS-INNOV Project during its implementation and for a period of 4 years after the end of the LEAPS_INNOV Project and which has been explicitly marked as “confidential” at the time of disclosure, or when disclosed orally has been identified as confidential at the time of disclosure and has been confirmed and designated in writing within 15 calendar days from oral disclosure at the latest as confidential information by the Disclosing Party, is Confidential Information.

Name:

I hereby agree to be appointed in my personal capacity as [External Expert in Work Package No. / member of the Innovation Advisory Board] for the LEAPS-INNOV Project (101004728) and to execute the task of supporting the LEAPS-INNOV Governing Board and/or Executive Board and/or Work Package in providing advice, reflections and ideas for the development of strategic issues honestly and fairly as defined in the LEAPS-INNOV Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement (Annex 1).

I commit to discussing questions put forward by the LEAPS-INNOV Project Coordinator or by the LEAPS-INNOV Project Governing Board and/or Executive Board and to provide recommendations in my field of expertise to the best of my ability and in the best interest of LEAPS-INNOV.

I hereby declare that I understand and accept the confidentiality obligations imposed on me as [External Expert / member of the Innovation Advisory Board/Work Package] of the LEAPS-INNOV Project as follows:

I acknowledge that all Confidential Information shall remain the property of the LEAPS-INNOV consortium. I have not been granted any rights, including intellectual property rights in respect of the Confidential Information, other than those expressly stated in this Declaration or in the case where prior written consent by the relevant Consortium Party/Parties has been obtained from the LEAPS-INNOV Coordinator.

I shall use the acquired Confidential Information for my given tasks only and shall not exploit or use it for my personal benefit or that of any third party.

I shall not divulge, publish or make available Confidential Information to any third party.

I shall exercise the same degree of care in protecting the Confidential Information as if it is my own; this includes ensuring that appropriate security measures are in place in relation to safekeeping of the Confidential Information.

I acknowledge that each Party of the LEAPS-INNOV Consortium Agreement listed in Annex 2 (Amendments possible) to this Confidentiality Declaration is entitled to promptly advise me in writing of any unauthorised disclosure, misappropriation or misuse of Confidential Information after it becomes aware of such unauthorised disclosure, misappropriation or misuse.

I acknowledge that the Declaration shall have effect as of the date of signature of this Declaration till the date my task is completed, or in case of an earlier termination if I receive written notice to this effect from the LEAPS-INNOV Coordinator, and that the confidentiality obligations shall last for four years after completion of the task or termination of the declaration.

I agree that on termination of my appointment, and at the request of LEAPS-INNOV Coordinator I will destroy, delete or return all Confidential Information within 15 days.

Done at..... Date.....

Signature:

